

Roles of Social Media in Sustaining Lifelong Learning for Efficiency in National Development

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Abstract:- Social media tools have become ubiquitous, with their usage being significant among higher-affiliated students. The most popular social media tools are Facebook, Wiki, YouTube, bulletin boards, LinkedIn, blogging, and Twitter. The advancement of modern technologies tries its best to accommodate the needs of people, especially the younger generation. The findings discovered that social media is crucially important in lifelong learning. It is cutting-edge and changes how people create, share, and participate in knowledge creation. Social media enhances the sharing of information and knowledge. It also enhances strategy in communication across time zones and continents. Social media provides a better platform to renew outdated information and knowledge. It facilitates information and knowledge sharing among people in different regions, races, and occupations. With social media, learning can always continue. Therefore, future technology integration in education should focus on what students use instead of what the school wants them to use to guarantee maximum efficiency. When students become the stakeholders of their learning, education will be genuinely revolutionized through effective collaboration between educators and students.

Keywords:- Social Media, Lifelong Learning, Efficiency, Collaboration, National Development.

I. INTRODUCTION

Technology has advanced from static information distribution to massive interaction among users. This advancement has widely been attributed to the development of Web 2.0, which features more user-generated content and usability for end users than its predecessor, Web 1.0. With the development of Web 2.0, one significant effect it had was spreading social software, as it gave opportunities to web developers to create more interactive applications and websites. It also enabled designers to implement their work in the online context better while the education sector began using more digital-orientated or digital-mediated educational programs (LeNoueHall and Eighmy, 2010). Web 2.0 technologies are emerging daily, even though there are already more than enough applications.

As social activities occur more and more around the digital world, as a result of the technological advances in the past years related to handheld devices (smartphones, phablets, tablets, etc.), traditional teaching will have to find

a means to make use of these features, that technology has to offer, in order to better contribute to individual learning, lifelong learning, and society in general. The application of these technologies in the education sector can be fully online or blended learning programs or even face-to-face learning as teaching material by tutors/instructors.

Lifelong learning is the process of continual development and changes over the lifespan in response to various motivators, from environmental change, vocational needs, life challenges, and health crises to curiosity and interest. Given all the possible motivators for learning, it is unsurprising that there are varied approaches to lifelong learning and contexts in which it can occur.

Numerous studies have examined the relationship between social media and life-long learning. Studies found that as a tool, social media makes a deep impact and profound meaning on life-long learning (Prensky, 2011; Guess, 2008). Also, social media tools facilitate the effects of life-long learning. This paper examines social media's role in sustaining lifelong learning for efficiency.

II. CONCEPT OF LIFELONG LEARNING

Learning in a lifetime is considered a social platform from which we expect all sorts of possibilities and opportunities for learning. Lifelong learning is a series of self-directed activities (the behavioural component) paired with information-seeking abilities that are started with persistent motivation (predisposition to learn) and the capacity to self-identify individual learning needs (the cognitive component). According to Hojat, Nasca, Erdmann, Frisby, Veloski, and Gonnella (2013), "Life-long learning is the development of human potential in the areas of knowledge, values, and skills, through a continuously supportive process that is stimulating and empowering, thus, fostering confidence, creativity, and enjoyment in all roles and circumstances.

One primary lifelong learning tool is self-directed learning (SDL), particularly outside structured educational settings. Self-direction supports control over the timing of learning, spacing of learning, and the order of information (Voss et al., 2011), which improves motivation to learn while solving problems (Leotti, Iyengar, & Ochsner, 2010). It also allows learners to concentrate attention and effort on specific knowledge goals that are currently required (Markant & Gureckis, 2010).

The knowledge and abilities required in today's world include those acquired outside formal education, making lifelong learning a crucial component of modern living. For instance, UNESCO (2012) went beyond what may be thought of as the usual curriculum for formal education and offered four learning pillars, including learning to know, do, live together, and be. This more profound type of learning is essential for the depth of change necessary for sustainable development.

Life-long learning is an open school for those who desire knowledge and personal improvement, social inclusion, self-sustainability, competitiveness, and employability. Life-long learning removes the restrictions, like some learning activities are for specific age groups or certain groups of people with particular identities. Life-long learning offers excellent opportunities for people to improve their potential (Demirel, 2003). Also, lifelong learning is not restricted to a specific time or place. With lifelong learning, we can learn at anytime and anywhere.

III. CONCEPT OF SOCIAL MEDIA

Social media is a computer-based technology that facilitates sharing of ideas, thoughts, and information through virtual networks and communities. Social media is internet-based and allows users to share anything quickly, including movies, images, documents, and personal information. Through web-based software or applications, users interact with social media on a computer, tablet, or smartphone (Digital Marketing Institute, 2021). People can use those platforms to create, share, and disseminate information, ideas, and knowledge with one another. It is the future of communications. It is a revolutionary point that changes how people create, share, and participate in information and knowledge. Although it does enhance the sharing of information and knowledge, it also enhances pedagogy in communication across time zones and continents. Social media is influencing not only individual users but also educational users.

Social media tools allow students to share their viewpoints, problems, and knowledge with others, teachers, and educators and be capable of improving studying and activity processes. Social media is a wonderful communication tool (Liu, 2010). Educators are increasingly finding it necessary to use these tools in learning and teaching together because many advantages exist in these public resources. In addition, using social media can quickly transfer the traditional investment in technology to a universal way.

IV. CONCEPT OF LEARNING EFFICIENCY

At the governmental, local, and personal levels, education is crucial. These educational opportunities benefit society and the individual, and in many nations, they are at least partially funded by the public coffers. Therefore, education must be delivered as effectively as feasible given the competing demands on government money.

According to Afonso and St Aubyn (2015), efficiency occurs when scholarly outputs (such as test scores) are created using the least resources, such as money or students' intrinsic skills. As a result, learning efficiency quantifies how much a person learns in a given time while improving their performance accuracy and speed.

Performance improvement is improving a learner's accuracy and speed due to that learner's interaction with a learning program. Learning efficiency measures academic progress that considers performance improvement and the student's learning time (Afonso and St Aubyn, 2015).

V. SOCIAL MEDIA AND LIFE-LONG LEARNING

Merriam and Caffarella (1999) suggest that "learning is a personal process...the context of adult life and the social context shape what an adult needs and wants to learn and, to a somewhat lesser extent, when and where learning takes place". Therefore, pedagogy can be improved by connecting with social media. In the same vein, we can find the relationship between social media and life-long learning in off-class or distance learning (Terry & Yolanda, 2015). For example, we often use networking or ongoing learning to learn before lectures and review after the class. Kind et al. (2013) summarized that 'social media can extend real-life learning and relationships into a shared space to foster professional growth.'

The essential characteristic of social media is in its nature. Based on its characteristics, knowledge can be shared not only at the same time but also asynchronously via dialogues, videos, and other social media tools. As a result, learners can exchange their ideas, issues, and goals with their peers, educators, and mentors with an interactive nature, actual or virtual, and will have duty partners in the learning and practice enhancement process. In addition, social media has excellent potential to resolve traditional hierarchies; for instance, learners who use microblogs can study from many blogs and propose their questions behind the blogs that can be convenient for bloggers to answer.

To be an experienced educator is to develop life-long learning in others (Schön, 2010). Therefore, precisely as Cheston et al. (2013) opined, it will be beneficial for extending online social networking development feedback by engagement in the learning process and improving collaboration. At the same time, through online blogs and other discussions, social media tools can also provide a platform, such as a forum for the reflection of learners. In this article, we will look at the situations that enhance life-long learning within some instances of social media reported in the literature.

VI. ROLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN SUSTAINING LIFELONG LEARNING FOR EFFICIENCY

Social networks, or social media in general, have an increasing impact on education through the tools available in a technology-driven and knowledge-based society. The competencies and skills that users acquire are those of non-formal education. Recently, there have been lots of social media tools available to us. However, every tool has both advantages and disadvantages for educators and learners. Outlined below are some social media tools that are used in various situations for the improvement of life-long learning.

➤ *Social Networking Tools*

Social networking tools has a general method of fascinating learners. Facebook for instance with over 3 billion users in the world has an excellent potential to improve life-long learning if these tools are utilized to sustain pedagogy, like discussion squads or online forums between learners and educators. As Wang et al., (2012) opined, to enhance learning in ongoing education, social networking has been combined with other forms of social media, such as YouTube. In all kinds of educational situations, it has been described that social networking is the single tool for replenishing life-long learning. For example, Nanyang technological university WKW School of Communication and Information students in course H6729, Singapore, were offered a lecture by using Facebook to supplement a lecture during the day before recess week. As a result, all of the students in this course participate in the group. Although their response rate was poor (with more than twenty-five percent), the lecturer describes that ninety percent of participants found this helpful tool. Recently, Facebook has been used in many aspects of pedagogy, such as media and information science, to promote participation and improve the discussion between educators and learners (DiVall & Kirwin, 2012; Estus, 2010).

Facebook also has another function in that everything that we upload through Facebook will be retained in Facebook's Servicer, and that will be public if you do not use a privacy setting. For some activities, the limitation of some access to this is essential. Therefore, privacy setting up is necessary. However, on the other side, educators can do the utmost in this environment to attract learners to genuine learning. For instance, learners can improve the discussion forums or activities for the public and out for social issues or projects; they will not only pay attention to what peers think about but also keep a watchful eye on what public's opinions towards these. Nowadays, learners' learning could be more helpful for what society needs. However, just like Liu (2010) said that it could help learners ensure the information which is worthy and applicative by involving the community in the learning process, and it can also help them have a better understanding of the situation that information will be used to raise the worth of education.

➤ *Blogs & Microblogs.*

By using blogs, learners can give their questions about the blogs, and bloggers (educators) can answer them in turn. During this interaction, a close relationship between

bloggers and learners is built. However, the factor is that most bloggers' opinions can be challenging for readers, and many blogs are more like diaries rather than a way of teaching. Blogs can be an excellent potential learning tool without these disadvantages. Pinilla et al., (2013) said that students in the school had used blogs to share and gain recommendations for preparing the tests. Genes and Parekh (2010) told us that it had been an efficient way to attract students and afford them the resource using a blog to improve the practice in a discussion format that allows the learners to have an efficient way to use the quickly seeking format.

Blogs often have some hyperlinks to other helpful text; in this way, learners can use the information in the blog immediately, and if necessary, it can allow the learners to mine further knowledge about the topic by themselves. In addition, when blogs include links to the review of peers, just like when it has been used for education association, the references are available to the learners to employ over time. These advantages make blogs an excellent tool for learning on your time.

Moreover, further echo about the blog and extending to additional blogs are allowed, which can message future blogs and other ways of learning. Microblogs and blogs are similar; they provide a platform for exchanging information and feedback. The transient nature of the message is the most prominent different characteristic between them, but it also gives limitations to blogs since the count – is often less than 140 characters. Numerous microblog platforms are available worldwide; they vary in this aspect, whether used in public or private groups. Wang (et al., 2013) said that, in China, students always use the microblog Sina Weibo to finish their tasks in group discussions, improving their satisfaction and participation. In this instance, educators traced students that participated in this survey. More than eighty percent of them considered that the microblog enhanced communication and most of them also considered that it improved interaction. Bahner et al., (2012) got the most pleasant surprise that even the students who had not used Twitter or other microblogs found the platform friendly and the information was valid. Twitter also has been used as 'live tweeting,' combining scientific and educational.

➤ *Online Education Tools.*

The option of video-based, multimedia interactive courses to replenish and improve teaching in the individuals because of the enhancement of today's technology. YouTube is a typical online site that can share information or knowledge via video. YouTube has more than 1 billion visitors each month, becoming the 4th most important website in the world today. Teacher-Tube is a unique channel that YouTube has dedicated to educators, which not only uploads instructional materials but also shares them with other educators. By using YouTube, educators and learners can get excellent resources. In addition, YouTube EDU was published by YouTube, which is defined as another education-related site that synthesizes a lot of free lectures from nearly 400 universities in the USA. However, it was influenced by MIT's open-source initiative in the

early years. It also allows educators and learners to access all worthy learning substances for free. While Arrington (2009) told us that knowledge spreading is prominent, and collecting and highlighting the tremendous educational substance will be a better way, which is uploaded to YouTube. As we all know, the creative use of science has no limits for creative minds.

YouTube is full of characteristics that can help educators with content exchange. For instance, YouTube can improve oral presentation; it can translate the video's caption into another language, which enhances the conversation of learners who use another language. At the same time, it also allows everyone to add videos at any location to improve teaching. Due to its convenience, YouTube has become a learning tool too. YouTube is available for everyone, wherever it has the Internet. The most significant difference between YouTube and iTunes podcasts is that YouTube does not need a third-party application to manage the content or browser package. For example, a research study (Liu, Y., 2010) conducted at the UH in the spring of 2009 involved a large chemistry class using both YouTube and iTunes Podcasts. The results showed that over seventy percent of the students were using YouTube, and less than thirty percent were using iTunes Podcasts. The simple reason is that YouTube is more convenient to use.

However, there is a precaution that students need to understand; whether its content is believable if all of the public material is used for educational purposes when YouTube is used as a learning resource. Therefore, not only do educators need to confirm the reliability of the source, but also the learners need to investigate the credibility of it to make sure the data are precise and effective, and also, by using this social media, Learners can enhance their analytical ability.

VII. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, using social media for learning is essential because people will spend more and more time in front of technologically driven social applications due to technological advances. After all, time has become a resource in itself, and people prefer to use it more efficiently.

It was concluded that social media is crucially important in lifelong learning. It is cutting-edge, changing how people create, share, and participate in information and knowledge. It also pushes people to a new point where they change how they share information. Also, it enhances pedagogy in communication across time zones and continents. Social media provides a better platform to renew outdated information and knowledge. It facilitates information and knowledge sharing among people in different regions, religions, races, occupations, etc. With social media, learning can always continue. It will bring human technology to another total revolution.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the study's findings, it is recommended that; future technology integration in education should focus on what students use instead of what the school wants them to use to guarantee maximum efficiency. When students become the stakeholders of their learning, education will be genuinely revolutionized through effective collaboration between educators and students.

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